

STUDY OF REUSING AC OUTLET WATER AND/OR COOLING PLANTS TO REDUCE AMBIENT TEMPERATURE OF AC

R. ATUL, VIII D

**CHINMAYA VIDYALAYA SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL
CHENNAI 600092**

PROBLEM

- Use of air conditioners increases day and night external temperatures
- Residential window and split AC external FAN units have higher ambient temperature near them
- Multiple units can cause overall increase of temperature

THOUGHTS

- Will a cool screen or cloth reduce the ambient temperature?
- Can the AC water be reused? If insufficient can non potable water be used to cool the external cooling systems if the through the experiment temperature is reduced?
- Can we use cooling plants around these units to reduce the temperature?

SCIENCE CONCEPTS

- Capillary Action
- Evaporation by heat absorption

INNOVATION

TESTING MODEL

READINGS

CASE 1 – NO SCREEN

- Readings were observed on a Voltas 1.0 ton Split AC unit without the screen

	Room Temperature	Heat Source	30 cm Away from AC unit
Voltas 1.0T Split AC	29°C	32.7°C	32.7°C
After a time Period	29°C	33.5°C	33.4°C

NEGLIGIBLE / NO REDUCTION OF TEMPERATURE

READINGS

CASE 2- WITH SCREEN

- Readings observed on a Hitachi 1.0 ton Window AC unit and Voltas 1.0T Split Unit with the Screen

	Room Temperature Heat Source		Near the screen
Hot Blower	30°C	42.4°C	41.6°C
Voltas 1.0T Split AC	29°C	31°C	29.4°C
After a time Period	29°C	32.4°C	31.6°C
Hitachi 1.0T Window AC	30°C	34.1°C	33.7°C
After Some time	31°C	34.9°C	34°C

REDUCTION OF TEMPERATURE OBSERVED

READINGS

CASE 3 - WITH SCREEN & COOLING PLANTS

- Readings observed on a Voltas 1.0T Split Unit with the Screen and Aloe Vera Plants

	Room Temperature	Heat Source	Plants & Screen
Reading 1	29.9°C	33.6°C	32.4°C
Reading 2	29.8°C	33.2°C	30.9°C
Reading 3	27.2°C	33.7°C	30.7°C

MORE TEMPERATURE REDUCTION WAS OBSERVED

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF TEMPERATURE REDUCTION

OBSERVATIONS

- There is a 0.6 – 0.8 degrees heat reduction for any type of AC with the Screen
- Better temperature reduction can be achieved by keeping cooling plants near the fan units of Split ACs
- Temperature reduction is influenced by the amount of open space near the AC. Reduction was found more with free space around (Split AC) and less with buildings close by (Window AC) in the test environment.

DRAWBACKS

- AC Outlet water evaporates faster than the speed of refill. External non-potable water addition or two units water used for one AC cooling screen can be considered as alternative. Still a decrease in temperature was witnessed due to the semi wet cloth acting like a heat sink.
- The frame should be made with a higher gauge thicker metal for stability and balance
- The rods supporting the frame should be clamped with screws to AC else it is found to be unstable
- The metal frame is not made with equal weight distribution hence it was tilting to one side
- Better sealing methods to be used to avoid water leakage from the screen unit.

SCOPE FOR FURTHER STUDY

Following 2 could not be done due to lack test environment

- Usage of electricity units when the frame is connected to be observed .
- Observations can be made with climbers on the system.

More to study....

- Cooling Plants effect can be studied independently
- Different screen cloth material can be studied
- Different water sources can be identified

CONCLUSION

- Implementation of screen to the AC unit reduces the external temperature as seen from the observations
- Addition of cooling plants improve the reduction of temperature.

Thank
you!

